

1 **The Low Density Matter (LDM) beamline at FERMI:**
 2 **optical layout and first commissioning**

3 CRISTIAN SVETINA,^{a,b} CESARE GRAZIOLI,^{c,d,e*} NICOLA MAHNE,^a
 4 LORENZO RAIMONDI,^a CLAUDIO FAVA,^a MARCO ZANGRANDO,^{a,d}
 5 SIMONE GERUSINA,^a MICHELE ALAGIA,^d LORENZO AVALDI,^f
 6 GIUSEPPE CAUTERO,^a MONICA DE SIMONE,^d MICHELE DEVETTA,^g MICHELE DI
 7 FRAIA,^h MARCEL DRABBELS,ⁱ VITALY FEYER,^a PAOLA FINETTI,^a
 8 RAPHAEL KATZY,^j ANTTI KIVIMÄKI,^d VIKTOR LYAMAYEV,^k TOMMASO MAZZA,^k
 9 ANGELICA MOISE,^a THOMAS MÖLLER,^l PATRICK O'KEEFFE,^f
 10 YEVHENIY OVCHARENKO,^l PAOLO PISERI,^g OKSANA PLEKAN,^a KEVIN
 11 C. PRINCE,^a RUDI SERGO,^a FRANK STIENKEMEIER,^j STEFANO STRANGES,^{m,d}
 12 MARCELLO CORENO^{n,a} AND CARLO CALLEGARI^a

13 ^a*Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste, Trieste, I-34149, Italy,* ^b*Graduate School of*
 14 *Nanotechnology, University of Trieste, I-34127 Trieste, Italy,* ^c*Department of*
 15 *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Trieste, 34127 Trieste, Italy,*
 16 ^d*CNR-IOM TASC, Area Science Park Basovizza, Trieste I-34149, Italy,* ^e*Laboratory*
 17 *of Quantum Optics, University of Nova Gorica, Nova Gorica, Slovenia,* ^f*CNR-ISM,*
 18 *Area della Ricerca di Roma 1, Monterotondo Scalo I-00015, Italy,* ^g*Dipartimento di*
 19 *Fisica, Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy,* ^h*Department of Physics,*
 20 *University of Trieste, Trieste, Italy,* ⁱ*EPFL, Lausanne, CH-1015, Switzerland,*
 21 ^j*University of Freiburg, Freiburg D-79085, Germany,* ^k*European XFEL, Hamburg*
 22 *D-22607, Germany,* ^l*TU Berlin, Berlin, D-10623, Germany,* ^m*Sapienza Università*
 23 *di Roma, Roma, I-00185, Italy, and* ⁿ*CNR-ISM, Area Science Park, Trieste*
 24 *I-34149, Italy. E-mail: cesare.grazioli@elettra.eu*

1

2

Beamline, Free electron laser, low density matter, photon transport, metrology

3

Abstract

4 The Low Density Matter (LDM) beamline has been built as part of the FERMI
5 Free Electron Laser (FEL) facility to serve the atomic, molecular, and cluster physics
6 community. After the commissioning phase, it received the first external users at the
7 end of 2012. The design and characterization of the LDM photon transport system is
8 described, detailing the optical components of the beamline.

9

1. Introduction

10 The Low Density Matter beamline (LDM) is an instrument for experiments involv-
11 ing molecular beams in combination with XUV/soft-X-ray radiation produced by the
12 FERMI FEL; the layout of FERMI and the main properties of its light (high bril-
13 liance, short pulse length, variable polarization, coherence) have been described before
14 (Allaria et al., 2010; Allaria et al., 2012) and are summarized in Table 1. The 100–4 nm
15 wavelength range is covered by two distinct light sources: the long wavelength FEL-1
16 (100–20 nm) and the short wavelength FEL-2 (20–4 nm). The photon beam paths of
17 the two sources merge in the safety hutch and are transported to the experimental
18 section via a common set of optics. The beamline was commissioned in 2012 and is
19 undergoing rapid development. A modular end-station (Lyamayev et al., 2013) for the
20 production of supersonic beams of atoms, molecules or clusters has been installed. The
21 beamline is now open to external users and the first experimental results have been
22 published (LaForge et al., 2014; Ovcharenko et al., 2014; Mazza et al., 2014; Žitnik
23 et al., 2014). This paper describes the parts of the LDM beamline not previously

1 reported (Allaria *et al.*, 2010; Lyamayev *et al.*, 2013), in the following sections: Photon
 2 transport system, Optics characterization, Focusing performance, Beamline transmis-
 3 sion and geometrical losses, Commissioning and present status of the beamline.

Table 1. *FEL-1 and FEL-2 parameters. See also (Giannessi *et al.*, 2012; Allaria *et al.*, 2015)*

Parameter	Value		Units
	FEL-1	FEL-2	
Wavelength ^d	100–20	20–4	nm
Pulse Length (FWHM) ^c	30–100	< 100	fs
4 Bandwidth (FWHM) ^a	1×10^{-3}		
Polarization	variable		
Repetition Rate	10 ^a ; 50 ^d		Hz
Energy/pulse ^a	> 50	> 10	μJ
Divergence (rms)*	1.25 λ	1.5 λ	μrad

^aachieved; ^ccalculated; ^ddesign; * λ in nm.

5 2. Photon transport system

6 The photon analysis, delivery, and reduction system (PADReS) consists of the section
 7 of the machine from the exit of the undulators to the endstations. A set of plane
 8 mirrors (PM1a and PM1b serving FEL-1; PM2a serving FEL-2) is installed in the
 9 so-called safety hutch. Each FEL source has its own beam-diagnostics and beam-
 10 conditioning instruments, such as the intensity and beam position monitors, beam
 11 defining apertures, and gas absorber (Zangrando *et al.*, 2009). At the end of the safety
 12 hutch the two photon beam paths enter the PM1b chamber (see Fig. 1), where one or
 13 the other can be selected.

14 Fig. 1. The photon beam transport and diagnostics system of FERMI. The two FEL
 15 undulator lines are visible on the left, inside the safety hutch (dashed line). The
 16 LDM endstation is in the bottom-right corner. The parameters of the optics are
 reported in Table 2

1 Outside the safety hutch, the energy spectrometer PRESTO (Svetina et al., 2011)
2 records the spectrum of each pulse by diffracting and detecting 1–2% of the total
3 intensity, while delivering the essentially unperturbed beam downstream. It employs
4 two plane substrates, ruled as gratings only in their central parts (60 mm over a
5 total length of 250 mm). The rulings have a variable line spacing along the longitu-
6 dinal direction (along the photon beam propagation direction) in order to focus the
7 diffracted radiation onto a movable two-dimensional detector that tracks the focal
8 curve. A computer calculates the one dimensional spectrum from the image, as well
9 as the central wavelength, bandwidth, horizontal and vertical projection on a shot-
10 by-shot basis, and this information can be stored with the experimental data. The
11 two gratings cover the whole wavelength range of FERMI as provided by FEL-1 (low
12 energy grating, LE) and FEL-2 (high energy grating, HE).

13 A split-and-delay line (AC/DC: AutoCorrelator/Delay Creator) is installed after
14 the spectrometer, for pump and probe experiments. It is based on the splitting and
15 subsequent recombination of the incoming wavefront after passing through two dif-
16 ferent branches (one of variable length, the other of fixed length), by means of eight
17 Au-coated plane mirrors, four for each path. In the variable length branch, two mir-
18 rors move on 900 mm-long linear guides with an accuracy of 10 μm , as measured by an
19 optical encoder. Changing the positions of these two mirrors produces a difference of
20 the two path lengths and introduces a time delay variable between -1.5 ps and 30 ps in
21 steps of 0.3 fs. The mirrors of the two branches operate with two different grazing inci-
22 dence angles: 2° in the fixed branch, 3° in the variable branch. This difference results in
23 different transmission coefficients of the light, which have been calculated considering
24 perfect mirrors (flat and free of contamination). For the fixed-length branch the trans-
25 mission of the 4 mirrors, in the wavelength range from 4 to 100 nm is about 80% for
26 radiation in S polarization and about 50–65% for P polarization. The transmission of

1 the other branch is about 70% for S polarization and about 30–50% for P polarization.
2 For selected wavelength ranges, the length of each branch can be further extended by
3 inserting 4 more multilayer (ML) mirrors operating at 45° incidence, thus introducing
4 an additional delay variable between 0.3 ns and 1.3 ns. The type of multilayers must be
5 chosen according to the experimental needs; we note that even at their design wave-
6 length, four additional ML mirrors reduce considerably the light transmission. Seven
7 out of eight mirrors have motorised pitch and roll movements, providing a fine control
8 of the alignment and the attainment of very good spatial overlap of the half beams in
9 the experimental stations. Overlap is visually evaluated by inspecting the two beams
10 on a YAG screen at the center of the end-station, and later optimized by maximiz-
11 ing a suitable experimental signal. It is possible to filter the radiation independently
12 in the two branches of the AC/DC unit: before the recombination mirror, an easily
13 accessible section that can host three filters for each branch gives users the possibility
14 of mounting filters suited to their experimental needs. To install filters from air into
15 vacuum requires a downtime of about twelve hours.

16 The 3-way switching mirror chamber selects which beamline is in use. The plane
17 switching mirror (SW) serving LDM deflects the beam in the horizontal direction,
18 and has a dual coating (graphite and iridium, each covering half the width of the
19 mirror), to maximise the reflectivity for FEL-1 and FEL-2, respectively. Downstream
20 of the switching mirror, the beam undergoes three further reflections: from a vertical
21 deflecting mirror (VD) and from two Kirkpatrick-Baez (K-B) mirrors.

22 The K-B system consists of two thin plane mirrors clamped at their sides and bent
23 via two mechanical pushers acting independently on their respective clamp in order
24 to attain the best elliptical profile as shown in Figure 5 of Reference (Raimondi *et al.*,
25 2013). The Kirkpatrick-Baez configuration (Kirkpatrick & Baez, 1948), decouples the
26 horizontal and vertical focusing. The active shape allows users to finely adjust the focal

1 length, making provision for the fact that the position of the last undulator (i.e., the
 2 nominal source points) of FEL-1 and FEL-2 differ by ~ 7 m. Likewise, the K-B active
 3 optics can compensate and correct astigmatism and defocusing effects originating from
 4 non-ideal profiles of the preceding plane mirrors, that are discussed in the next section.

Table 2. *Parameters of the optics; d : distance from the nominal source points (FEL-1/FEL-2); w : width; ℓ : length; θ : grazing incidence angle. PM2a and SW have two coatings, each covering half the width of the mirror, and their position can be adjusted sidewise to use one or the other coating. Orientation (H, V) refers to the deflection plane.*

Mirror	d (m)	$w \times \ell$ (mm \times mm)	θ ($^\circ$)	Coating	Shape (orientation)
PM1a	48.1/–	20 \times 400	2.5	Graphite	plane (H)
5 PM1b	54.3/–	20 \times 250	5	Graphite	plane (H)
PM2a	–/41.4	20 \times 300	2.5	Graphite/Ni	plane (H)
PRESTO-LE	57.5/49.8	20 \times 250	2.5	Graphite	VLS plane grating (H)
PRESTO-HE	57.5/49.8	20 \times 250	2.5	Au	VLS plane grating (H)
SW	77.5/69.9	25 \times 480	2	Graphite/Ir	plane (H)
VD	90.0/82.3	20 \times 390	2	Au	plane (V)
H-KB	95.6/87.9	40 \times 400	2	Au	active (V)
V-KB	96.1/88.5	40 \times 400	2	Au	active (H)

6 2.1. Optics characterization

7 All the optics described above were characterised in the Elettra metrology labora-
 8 tory by means of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and white-light interferometry, to
 9 cover the spatial high-frequency range (10 μm – 1 mm) and determine the roughness.
 10 The rms roughness has been measured to be below 2 \AA , small enough to consider the
 11 surface scattering negligible, as verified during the commissioning of the beamline.
 12 The spatial low frequencies (from 0.5 mm to the length of the mirror) of the optical
 13 surfaces, i.e., the slopes and figures, have been measured with a Long Trace Profiler
 14 (LTP) (Rommeveaux *et al.*, 2008). All optics meet specifications and a summary of
 15 the results of the metrological inspection (residual radius of curvature, Peak-to-Valley
 16 and Slope error rms) for the plane mirrors is reported in Table 3.

Table 3. *Measured optical parameters: R: radius of curvature; Res PtV: residual peak-to-valley displacement after best-sphere subtraction; Res Slope error: residual slope error (rms) after best-sphere subtraction.*

Mirror	R (km)	Res PtV (nm)	Res Slope error (μ rad)
1 PM1a	42.3	120	0.89
PM1b	10.6	46.5	0.56
PM2a	28.1	135	0.95
PRESTO-LE	29.7	36	0.44
PRESTO-HE	27.1	22	0.45
SW	34	78.5	0.59
VD	154.6	42.3	0.32

2 The mechanical bending system of the two K-B mirrors has also been tested and
3 optimized using the Adaptive Correction Tool software (ACT) (Signorato et al., 1999).
4 The best profiles, i.e., those closest to the nominal elliptical form, have been achieved
5 (Raimondi et al., 2013); their sagittas (distance from the centre of the arc formed by
6 the mirror to the base of the arc) have been measured to be $\sim 230 \mu\text{m}$ for the horizontal
7 focusing mirror, and $\sim 160 \mu\text{m}$ for the vertical focusing mirror. The presence of residual
8 radii of curvature, slope errors and figure errors may cause a variation of the actual
9 focal distance and intensity distribution of the virtual source seen by the K-B focusing
10 system that is discussed in the next section.

11 2.2. Focusing performance

12 Calculations of the expected spot size and shape have been carried out for both
13 sources (FEL-1 and FEL-2) in their whole wavelength range, using the codes SHADOW
14 (Sanchez del Rio et al., 2011), based on ray tracing, and WISE (Raimondi et al., 2015),
15 based on physical optics. The sources have been modelled as Gaussian beams, with the
16 measured values of the FERMI radiation (source size, divergence, beam propagation
17 factor M^2) as input parameters. The beams were propagated along PADReS (both
18 “ideal” and “as measured” mirrors are considered); there is good agreement between
19 the physical-optics and the ray-tracing approach except for some diffraction effects
20 absent in the latter simulations.

1 Calculated spot profiles in the case of smallest spot size ($4\mu\text{m} \times 6\mu\text{m}$ FWHM for
 2 FEL-1 and $3\mu\text{m} \times 5\mu\text{m}$ FWHM for FEL-2) are shown in Fig. 2. Here the effect of the
 3 non-ideal mirror shape can be seen as a broadening of the spots and the appearance
 4 of some diffraction peaks. The unavoidable diffraction effect is due to the finite size
 5 of the substrates and gets smaller as the wavelength decreases; in any case the beam
 6 quality remains high, as experimentally confirmed during the commissioning phase.

7
 8
 9 Fig. 2. Simulated focal spots for the LDM beamline in the case of ideal (red) and real (blue) mirrors; WISE program was used. The intensity profiles are calculated for FEL-1 at 30 nm and FEL-2 at 4 nm, and are displayed along the vertical and the horizontal directions. The diffraction effect is due to the finite size of the mirrors. The smallest achievable spot sizes (FWHM) are predicted to be $\approx 4\mu\text{m} \times 6\mu\text{m}$ for FEL-1 and $\approx 3\mu\text{m} \times 5\mu\text{m}$ for FEL-2. The areas are all normalized to 1 in order to compare the size of the spot irrespective of the intensity of the incident beam.

10 We emphasize the great importance of the bendable K-B system in the focusing
 11 section. Besides the need to accommodate, as already mentioned, different source
 12 positions for FEL-1 and FEL-2, deviations of the transport optics from a perfect
 13 plane profile (slope errors) cause a variation of the distance and intensity distribution

1 of the virtual source as seen by the K-B mirrors. As an example: at 32.5 nm (FEL-1)
 2 we estimate that the virtual source becomes astigmatic with the horizontal and ver-
 3 tical waists located respectively about 9.70 m and 2.94 m downstream of the nominal
 4 position. This effect can be easily handled and compensated by properly changing the
 5 curvature of the K-B mirrors.

6 To conclude this section, we mention some techniques we adopt to optimize focusing
 7 of the photon beam according to the needs of the user. For less demanding experiments
 8 that tolerate a larger spot size (above $\approx 20\mu\text{m}$ FWHM) in exchange for easier, faster
 9 operation, we use a simple fluorescent screen (YAG, YAP, or phosphor) inserted at
 10 the nominal focal plane; we have also investigated the use of multi-photon ionization
 11 of rare gas atoms as a quick feedback signal (see Sec. 3).

Fig. 3. The left panel shows the best focal spot of $5 \times 8 \mu\text{m}^2$ obtained during the wavefront sensor measurement campaign. This spot is reconstructed via software from the wavefront measured 1 m out of focus behind the LDM end-station. The right panel shows the wavefront residuals (after tilt compensation and subtraction of the ideal propagation wavefront).

15 For studies requiring micro-focusing, the most informative diagnostic is a wavefront
 16 sensor (WFS) of the Hartmann-Shack type (Mercère *et al.*, 2003). The WFS is based

1 on an array of 13×13 mm² pin-holes coupled to a CCD camera (1024×1024 pixels;
2 pixel size 24×24 μm^2); the instrument allows the user to measure the wavefront at the
3 location of the array (in our case, 1.2 m downstream of the focal point, i.e., of the FEL-
4 sample interaction region); specifically, the wavefront sensor software calculates the
5 intensity distribution of the beam (typically a mix between several modes resulting in
6 a *noisy hyper-Gaussian* intensity profile) and the wavefront deviation (residual) from
7 the ideal propagation shape. For a reasonably smooth wavefront, dedicated software
8 back-propagates the result of the measurement to the focal point and reconstructs the
9 focal spot.

10 We performed a measurement campaign on the LDM end-station to ascertain the
11 influence of K-B mirror bending on spot size, and consequently refine the mirror shape,
12 as well as to confirm the accuracy of the WISE simulations. The wavefront residuals
13 allow an excellent optimization of the focal spot: the strategy is to flatten the wavefront
14 by bending the mirror and finely adjusting the system angles (i.e., pitch and roll of
15 K-B mirrors, and incidence angles of the light). In particular, in order to optimize
16 the mirror curvature we tried to minimize the aberrations that were quantified in
17 terms of Zernike coefficients. The Hartmann sensor software is able to compute these
18 coefficients; consequently it allows the operator to understand how to adjust on the
19 pusher motors in order to reduce the aberrations. It is indeed very easy to correct the
20 optical aberrations and reach the best wavefront profile (thus, focal spot) that this
21 mechanical system can attain. Fig. 3 shows a single-shot image of the best focal spot
22 achieved, at a FEL wavelength of 30 nm, with this technique: 5×8 μm^2 (FWHM).
23 In this case we obtain a wavefront residual rms of 9 nm. Simulations obtained with
24 the WISE code, and based on the ideal elastic deformation of the mirrors, produce
25 a focal spot of 4×6 μm^2 (FWHM); we conclude that with the wavefront sensor as a
26 feedback it is possible to bend the optics to perform very close to the ideal limit of

1 the mechanical system.

2 2.3. Beamline transmission and geometrical losses

3 Overall, in the basic configuration (delay line withdrawn) seven mirrors are used
 4 for FEL-1 and six for FEL-2. Using the parameters reported in Table 2 as input for
 5 the computer codes REFLEC (Schafers & Krumrey, 1996) and IMD (Windt, 1998),
 6 we calculated the reflectivity of each mirror for horizontal/vertical polarizations. The
 7 calculated overall transmission of the beamline (excluding geometrical losses) is shown
 8 in Fig. 4.

9
 10
 11 Fig. 4. Calculated transmission of the LDM beamline optics for the two FEL sources and the two linear polarizations (FEL-1: red traces; FEL-2: blue traces. Vertical polarization: solid traces; horizontal polarization: dotted traces). The mirrors delivering the photon beam to the LDM end-station are PM1a, PM1b, LE grating for FEL-1; PM2a and HE grating for FEL-2; mirrors SW, VD, H-KB, V-KB are common to both. The geometrical losses have been included in the calculation. The discontinuity at 41.3 nm is due to the use of two different databases: (Palik, 1997) and (Henke et al., 1993).

12 Due to the beamline geometry (five mirrors reflecting in the horizontal plane, two
 13 in the vertical plane for FEL-1; four and two for FEL-2) the vertical and horizon-

tal polarizations are not equally transmitted to the endstation, thus the ellipticity varies across the whole wavelength range. The linear horizontally polarized light suffers greater losses than the vertically polarized one. While this effect is negligible below 40 nm, above this wavelength it rapidly increases. The choice of APPLE-2 undulators for FERMI (Allaria *et al.*, 2014) allows smooth control of the polarization of the emitted radiation: i.e., one can set the FEL polarization to be elliptical upstream of the transport optics, in order to have circularly polarized radiation at the end-station (Allaria *et al.*, 2012; Allaria *et al.*, 2014).

The beam divergence in the far-field θ_{rms} is proportional to the wavelength λ (Table 1): as a consequence there are geometrical losses due to the finite size of the mirrors that can affect the overall transmission. These geometrical losses are higher at longer wavelengths and become negligible at shorter wavelengths. The geometrical acceptances at different wavelengths have been determined using ray tracing simulations, and are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. *Geometrical acceptance (due to the finite mirror sizes, and the photon beam divergence), reflectivity, and overall transmission of the photon beam transport system.*

Wavelength nm	FEL	θ_{rms} μrad	Geometrical acceptance %	Reflectivity %	Overall transmission
65	1	81.3	41.3	54.8	22.7
52	1	65	54.5	58.0	31.6
43	1	53.8	68.1	57.4	38.8
32	1	40	86.9	59.8	51.3
20	1	25	99.3	56.7	56.6
20	2	30	97.0	54.6	55.3
10	2	15	>99	64.5	65.0
8	2	12	>99	54.8	54.3
6	2	9	>99	12.0	11.9
4	2	6	>99	5.0	4.98

3. Commissioning and present status of the beamline

During the beamline construction period, commissioning measurements were performed with a prototype end-station equipped with a Velocity Map Imaging/ion time-of-flight spectrometer (VMI/TOF). The original VMI spectrometer and its further

1 improvements have been described previously(O’Keeffe et al., 2012).

2 One of the test measurements is shown in Fig. 5. At the time of the commissioning,
3 the FEL pulse length was 120 fs and the energy per pulse was 60 μ J. In order to test
4 the capabilities of the adjustable focusing system we measured ion TOF spectra of
5 Xe atoms exposed to FEL pulses, observing charge states indicative of multi-photon
6 absorption; the intensity ratio of different charge states as a function of time while
7 changing the bending of the K-B mirrors (inset to Fig. 5) is a good indicator of
8 the reproducibility of the focusing system for small curvature changes. While highly
9 charged states of Xe obtained upon FEL irradiation have been reported in the liter-
10 ature (Sorokin et al., 2007) for photon energies within the $4d \rightarrow \epsilon f$ giant resonance
11 (93 eV), to our knowledge only sequential double ionization of Xe has been reported
12 at 23.0 and 24.3 eV (Mondal et al., 2013), at average intensities of $2 - 3 \times 10^{13}$ W/cm².

1

2

3

Fig. 5. Ion time-of-flight (TOF) mass/charge spectra of Xe taken at $\lambda = 52.22$ nm (23.74 eV) for different focusing conditions. Each spectrum is a sum over several spectra; all spectra have been recorded with the same FEL intensity. In the inset (blue line) we show the $\text{Xe}^{2+}/\text{Xe}^+$ intensity ratio as a function of time while changing the curvature of the K-B mirrors.

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

The LDM beamline now features a modular end-station accommodating a broad range of systems for producing targets and detectors. The combined capabilities of the photon source (high-brilliance, short-pulse length, variable polarization, coherence), photon transport (variable-focusing optics) and endstation allow the investigation of many targets, such as very dilute systems, matter under extreme irradiation conditions (multiple electronic excitation, multiple ionization, Coulomb explosion, non-linear optics), and dichroism. The split-and-delay line described above, as well as a synchronized optical laser (Cinquegrana *et al.*, 2014) allow time-resolved experiments with different combinations of femtosecond pulses.

13

Acknowledgements The authors would like to acknowledge the contribution of the

1 entire FERMI team. Thanks are due to Dr. Robert Richter who contributed with his
 2 help and many insightful discussions. CC, CG and MC acknowledge support by the
 3 Italian Slovenian Crossborder Cooperation Programme (CITIUS project, 2013/2010090600115298).

4 **References**

- 5 Allaria, E. *et al.* (2010). *New J. Phys.* **12**(7), 075002.
 6 Allaria, E. *et al.* (2012). *Nature Photon.* **6**(10), 699–704.
 7 Allaria, E. *et al.* (2014). *Phys. Rev. X*. In press.
 8 Allaria, E. *et al.* (2015). *J. Synchrotron Radiat.* **sameissue**.
 9 Cinquegrana, P. *et al.* (2014). *Phys. Rev. ST Accel. Beams*, **17**, 040702.
 10 Giannessi, L. *et al.* (2012). *FEL 2012 - 34th International Free Electron Laser Conference*, pp.
 11 13–18.
 12 Henke, B. *et al.* (1993). *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables*, **54**, 181–342.
 13 Kirkpatrick, P. & Baez, A. V. (1948). *J. Opt. Soc. America*, **38**, 766–773.
 14 LaForge, A. C. *et al.* (2014). *Sci. Rep.* **4**, 3621.
 15 Lyamayev, V. *et al.* (2013). *J. Phys. B*, **46**, 164007.
 16 Mazza, T. *et al.* (2014). *Nature Commun.* **5**, 3648.
 17 Mercère, P. *et al.* (2003). *Optics Letters*, **28**, 1534–1536.
 18 Mondal, S. *et al.* (2013). *J. Phys. B*, **46**(16), 164022.
 19 O’Keeffe, P. *et al.* (2012). *Nucl. Instr. Meth. B*, **284**, 69.
 20 Ovcharenko, Y. *et al.* (2014). *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112**, 073401.
 21 Palik, E. (ed.) (1997). *Handbook of Optical Constants of Solids*. Academic Press.
 22 Raimondi, L. *et al.* (2013). *Nucl. Instrum. Methods A*, **710**, 131–138.
 23 Raimondi, L. *et al.* (2015). *Astronomy Astrophysics*, **573**, 1–19.
 24 Sanchez del Rio, M., Canestrari, N., Jiang, F. & Cerrina, F. (2011). *J. of Sync. Rad.* **18**(5),
 25 708–716.
 26 Rommeveaux, A. *et al.* (2008). In *Modern Developments in X-Ray and Neutron Optics*, edited
 27 by A. Erko, M. Idir, T. Krist & A. Michette, vol. 137 of *Springer Series in optical science*.
 28 Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
 29 Schafers, F. & Krumrey, M. (1996). REFLEC, a program to calculate VUV/X-ray optical
 30 elements and synchrotron radiation beamline. Technischer Bericht TB 201. BESSY.
 31 Signorato, R., Sole, V. A. & Gauthier, C. (1999). *J. Synchrotron Radiation*, **6**(3), 176–178.
 32 Sorokin, A. A., Bobashev, S. V., Feigl, T., Tiedtke, K., Wabnitz, H. & Richter, M. (2007).
 33 *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99**, 213002.
 34 Svetina, C. *et al.* (2011). *Proc. SPIE*, **8139**, 81390J.
 35 Žitnik, M. *et al.* (2014). *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**, 193201.
 36 Windt, D. (1998). *Computer in Physics*, **12**(4), 360–370.
 37 Zangrando, M. *et al.* (2009). *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **80**(11), 113110.

Synopsis

38

A description of the LDM beamline of FERMI is given, with a detailed description of the photon transport.
